

Swiss NGS bacterial typing ring trial - submission form

SIB Clinical Bioinformatics

Thank you for taking part in the Swiss NGS-based bacterial typing ring trial !

This questionnaire will let you upload your files and specify the methods that you used for the ring trial.

There are 38 questions in this survey

Sample prep, library prep, sequencing

Arrival and processing dates (dd.mm.yyyy) *

Please write your answer(s) here:

Date material received

Date processing the bacterial cultures started

Storage conditions of the e-swabs in the time between reception and processing *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 80°C
- 20°C
- 4°C
- Room Temperature
- No storage, processed immediately upon reception
- Other

Bacterial cultures conditions *

Please write your answer(s) here:

Type of agar media/liquid broth

Incubation time (hrs)

Incubation temperature (°C)

DNA extraction *

Please write your answer(s) here:

Kit/robot used

Duration of DNA extraction (hrs)

How was DNA quantified and qualified prior to library preparation? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Nanodrop
- Qubit/Quantus
- BioAnalyzer/Fragment Analyzer
- qPCR
- DNA was not quantified/qualified prior to library preparation
- Other:

DNA concentration, amount and quality (please answer only the rows that you actually measured)

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	S
DNA concentration (ng/ul)	<input type="text"/>						
DNA amount (micrograms)	<input type="text"/>						
260/280 ratio	<input type="text"/>						
260/230 ratio	<input type="text"/>						

Library preparation *

Please write your answer(s) here:

Kit name(s) (or citation of protocol if non-commercial kit)?	<input type="text"/>
Single-end or paired-end?	<input type="text"/>
Expected read length (bp)?	<input type="text"/>
Expected total number of reads/strain?	<input type="text"/>
Duration of library preparation (hrs)	<input type="text"/>

What sequencing platform did you use? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Illumina MiniSeq
- Illumina MiSeq
- Illumina NextSeq
- Illumina HiSeq 2500
- Illumina HiSeq 3000/4000
- Illumina HiSeq X5/10
- Illumina NovaSeq 5000/6000
- Ion Torrent PGM
- Ion Torrent S5
- Ion Torrent Proton
- MinION
- PacBio RS II
- PacBio Sequel System
- Other:

Duration of sequencing (hrs) *

Please write your answer here:

SNP calling, assembly

Were reads quality filtered before conducting the analysis? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No
 I don't know

Please specify how reads were quality filtered before conducting the analysis.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '10 [preproc0]' (Were reads quality filtered before conducting the analysis?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- cutadapt
 trimmomatic
 PrinSeq
 FastQC
 fastq-mcf
 pear
 Other:

Did you check for contamination and/or verify the species prior to the SNP analysis? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Which tool did you use to verify the species?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '12 [verify1]' (Did you check for contamination and/or verify the species prior to the SNP analysis?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- KmerFinder
 Reads2Type
 MetaPhlan
 Kraken
 Other:

For variant detection, which of the following approaches did you undertake? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Mapping of reads to a genome, followed by SNPs calling (no assembly-step needed to call SNPs)
 Reference-based assembly prior to calling SNPs
 De novo assembly prior to calling SNPs
 Other

How did you use the provided reference genome?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- We mapped the reads to the entire reference genome (SNP identification was not restricted to specific subsections of the reference genome)
 We mapped the reads to specific subsections of the reference genome (i.e. we used a "trimmed reference genome").
 We did not use the provided reference genome at all (oops... we'll repeat the analysis choosing one of the options above or explaining below another option)
 Other

How did you choose the subsections of the genome on which you mapped the reads?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'We mapped the reads to specific subsections of the reference genome (i.e. we used a "trimmed reference genome").' at question '15 [refgenome]' (How did you use the provided reference genome?)

Please write your answer here:

In addition to using the provided reference genome, did you also use an alternative approach to identify SNPs? *

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- No, we only used the provided reference genome.
- Yes, we also mapped the reads to one/several other reference genomes.
- Yes, and we explain how we proceeded in the comment box.

Please specify below for each sample the ID of the genome against which you mapped the reads.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '17 [refgenome2]' (In addition to using the provided reference genome, did you also use an alternative approach to identify SNPs?)

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	Sample 7
ID of genome used for mapping reads	<input type="text"/>						

Which tool did you use for mapping reads? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- bwa mem
- bowtie2
- STAR
- blastn
- Other:

If you performed assembly, please answer the following:

Please write your answer(s) here:

Which tool did you use? Please provide name including version.

Do you filter out contigs below a certain size? (if yes, please specify size)

Which tool(s) did you use to call SNPs? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Snippy/nullarbor
- SeqSphere
- CLC Genomics
- Samtools
- VCF tools
- Other:

Phylogenetics, resistance, virulence

Did you build your tree based on the: *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Whole genome?
 Core genome?
 Core SNP matrix?
 Other:

Which tool did you use to build the tree? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- FastTree
 RaxML
 PhyML
 FigTree
 Other:

Distance metric used *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Nb SNP differences
 JC
 REV
 GTR
 Other:

Algorithm *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Neighbor-joining
 UPGMA
 Bayesian
 Maximum likelihood
 Other:

**Please specify below the clusters of related strains that you identified among the cases, thank you. E.g.
cluster 1: strains x,y,z
cluster 2: strains ...**

*

Please write your answer here:

If you called resistance, please answer the following questions:

Please write your answer(s) here:

Name of the tool or short description if in-house

Database of resistance factors queried by the tool

Input (please specify if: NGS reads and/or genes)

If you called virulence, please answer the following questions

Please write your answer(s) here:

Name of the tool or short description if in-house

Database queried by the tool

Input (please specify if: NGS reads and/or genes)

You have 5 urgent *S. aureus* bacterial cultures. In how many hours could you provide a report on strain relatedness (i.e. duration from DNA extraction to report, under emergency conditions)? *

Please write your answer here:

Please write here any general comments on the ring trial, thank you.

Please write your answer here:

Data submission

I have named all the files using my lab pipeline letter and the strain number, e.g. B2.fasta, for the genome of strain 2 assembled with lab pipeline B.

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Submit data

You are about to proceed with data upload on a password-protected private cloud. Please note that we will ask you to upload your data to specific folders, as explained below:

- **FASTQ raw reads:** "FASTQ" folder - expected format: FASTQ
IMPORTANT: For a faster upload, we recommend that you compress the files before uploading them.
- **Genomes for mapping:** "Genomes for mapping" folder - expected format: FASTA
IMPORTANT: Please provide here all the genomes used for read mapping, i.e. entire genomes, or trimmed genomes obtained after e.g. computing a core genome or by excluding specific genomic regions.
IMPORTANT: If a core genome approach was undertaken, please provide as well the multiple sequence alignment, including the provided reference genome.
- **SNP positions (not-filtered and filtered):** "SNPs" folder - Expected format: VCF
IMPORTANT: Filtered SNPs: Please add **"-filtered"** at the end of the filename to specify a filtered list of SNPs, e.g. B2-filtered.vcf, and place it in the corresponding folder (SNPs/Filtered_SNP_positions).
IMPORTANT: If possible, please specify the SNPs positions using the coordinates of the provided reference genome.
- **Assembled genomes** (if applicable): "Assembled genomes" folder. Expected format: FASTA
- **Phylogenetic tree:** "Tree" folder. Expected formats: NEWICK, NEXUS, (FASTA)
IMPORTANT: Your tree should also contain the provided reference genome.
IMPORTANT: If your tree is based on a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of full/trimmed genomes, please provide as well in the "Tree" folder the MSA including the provided reference genome, in FASTA.
- **Resistance genes** (if applicable): "Resistance" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain
- **Virulence factors** (if applicable): "Virulence" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain
- **Lab reports:** "Report" folder. Expected formats: Word, OpenOffice, RTF or PDF.
IMPORTANT: the lab report is intended to be a document that may be shared with other clinical labs, and might thus contain technical/methodological details.

I have read carefully the above explanations and I am now ready to proceed with data upload.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [wa]' (I have named all the files using my lab pipeline letter and the strain number, e.g. B2.fasta, for the genome of strain 2 assembled with lab pipeline B.)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

ANALYSIS BASED ON MAPPING THE READS AGAINST THE PROVIDED REFERENCE GENOME

Please select below the lab pipeline for which you completed the survey (password-protected), and upload your data in the folders as explained above, thank you.

Pipeline A	Pipeline B	Pipeline C	Pipeline D
Pipeline E	Pipeline F	Pipeline G	Pipeline H
Pipeline I	Pipeline J	Pipeline K	Pipeline L
Pipeline M	Pipeline N	Pipeline O	Pipeline P
Pipeline Q	Pipeline R	Pipeline S	Pipeline T

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '36 [submit21]' (Submit data You are about to proceed with data upload on a password-protected private cloud. Please note that we will ask you to upload your data to specific folders, as explained below: FASTQ raw reads: "FASTQ" folder - expected format: FASTQ IMPORTANT: For a faster upload, we recommend that you compress the files before uploading them. Genomes for mapping: "Genomes for mapping" folder - expected format: FASTA IMPORTANT: Please provide here all the genomes used for read mapping, i.e. entire genomes, or trimmed genomes obtained after e.g. computing a core genome or by excluding specific genomic regions. IMPORTANT: If a core genome approach was undertaken, please provide as well the multiple sequence alignment, including the provided reference genome. SNP positions (not-filtered and filtered): "SNPs" folder - Expected format: VCF IMPORTANT: Filtered SNPs: Please add "-filtered" at the end of the filename to specify a filtered list of SNPs, e.g. B2-filtered.vcf, and place it in the corresponding folder (SNPs/Filtered_SNP_positions). IMPORTANT: If possible, please specify the SNPs positions using the coordinates of the provided reference genome. Assembled genomes (if applicable): "Assembled genomes" folder. Expected format: FASTA Phylogenetic tree: "Tree" folder. Expected formats: NEWICK, NEXUS, (FASTA) IMPORTANT: Your tree should also contain the provided reference genome. IMPORTANT: If your tree is based on a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of full/trimmed genomes, please provide as well in the "Tree" folder the MSA including the provided reference genome, in FASTA. Resistance genes (if applicable): "Resistance" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Virulence factors (if applicable): "Virulence" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Lab reports: "Report" folder. Expected formats: Word, OpenOffice, RTF or PDF. IMPORTANT: the lab report is intended to be a document that may be shared with other clinical labs, and might thus contain technical/methodological details. I have read carefully the above explanations and I am now ready to proceed with data upload.)

ADDITIONAL ANALYSIS, NOT BASED ON MAPPING THE READS AGAINST THE PROVIDED REFERENCE GENOME ONLY

Please select below the lab pipeline for which you completed the survey (password-protected), and upload your data in the folders as explained above, thank you.

Pipeline A	Pipeline B	Pipeline C	Pipeline D
Pipeline E	Pipeline F	Pipeline G	Pipeline H
Pipeline I	Pipeline J	Pipeline K	Pipeline L
Pipeline M	Pipeline N	Pipeline O	Pipeline P
Pipeline Q	Pipeline R	Pipeline S	Pipeline T

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '36 [submit21]' (Submit data You are about to proceed with data upload on a password-protected private cloud. Please note that we will ask you to upload your data to specific folders, as explained below: FASTQ raw reads: "FASTQ" folder - expected format: FASTQ IMPORTANT: For a faster upload, we recommend that you compress the files before uploading them. Genomes for mapping: "Genomes for mapping" folder - expected format: FASTA IMPORTANT: Please provide here all the genomes used for read mapping, i.e. entire genomes, or trimmed genomes obtained after e.g. computing a core genome or by excluding specific genomic regions. IMPORTANT: If a core genome approach was undertaken, please provide as well the multiple sequence alignment, including the provided reference genome. SNP positions (not-filtered and filtered): "SNPs" folder - Expected format: VCF IMPORTANT: Filtered SNPs: Please add "-filtered" at the end of the filename to specify a filtered list of SNPs, e.g. B2-filtered.vcf, and place it in the corresponding folder (SNPs/Filtered_SNP_positions). IMPORTANT: If possible, please specify the SNPs positions using the coordinates of the provided reference genome. Assembled genomes (if applicable): "Assembled genomes" folder. Expected format: FASTA Phylogenetic tree: "Tree" folder. Expected formats: NEWICK, NEXUS, (FASTA) IMPORTANT: Your tree should also contain the provided reference genome. IMPORTANT: If your tree is based on a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of full/trimmed genomes, please provide as well in the "Tree" folder the MSA including the provided reference genome, in FASTA. Resistance genes (if applicable): "Resistance" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Virulence factors (if applicable): "Virulence" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Lab reports: "Report" folder. Expected formats: Word, OpenOffice, RTF or PDF. IMPORTANT: the lab report is intended to be a document that may be shared with other clinical labs, and might thus contain technical/methodological details. I have read carefully the above explanations and I am now ready to proceed with data upload.) and Answer was at question '17 [refgenome2]' (In addition to using the provided reference genome, did you also use an alternative approach to identify SNPs?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '36 [submit21]' (Submit data You are about to proceed with data upload on a password-protected private cloud. Please note that we will ask you to upload your data to specific folders, as explained below: FASTQ raw reads: "FASTQ" folder - expected format: FASTQ IMPORTANT: For a faster upload, we recommend that you compress the files before uploading them. Genomes for mapping: "Genomes for mapping" folder - expected format: FASTA IMPORTANT: Please provide here all the genomes used for read mapping, i.e. entire genomes, or trimmed genomes obtained after e.g. computing a core genome or by excluding specific genomic regions. IMPORTANT: If a core genome approach was undertaken, please provide as well the multiple sequence alignment, including the provided reference genome. SNP positions (not-filtered and filtered): "SNPs" folder - Expected format: VCF IMPORTANT: Filtered SNPs: Please add "-filtered" at the end of the filename to specify a filtered list of SNPs, e.g. B2-filtered.vcf, and place it in the corresponding folder (SNPs/Filtered_SNP_positions). IMPORTANT: If possible, please specify the SNPs positions using the coordinates of the provided reference genome. Assembled genomes (if applicable): "Assembled genomes" folder. Expected format: FASTA Phylogenetic tree: "Tree" folder. Expected formats: NEWICK, NEXUS, (FASTA) IMPORTANT: Your tree should also contain the provided reference genome. IMPORTANT: If your tree is based on a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of full/trimmed genomes, please provide as well in the "Tree" folder the MSA including the provided reference genome, in FASTA. Resistance genes (if applicable): "Resistance" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Virulence factors (if applicable): "Virulence" folder. Expected format: FASTA for genes sorted by strain Lab reports: "Report" folder. Expected formats: Word, OpenOffice, RTF or PDF. IMPORTANT: the lab report is intended to be a document that may be shared with other clinical labs, and might thus contain technical/methodological details. I have read carefully the above explanations and I am now ready to proceed with data upload.) and Answer was at question '17 [refgenome2]' (In addition to using the provided reference genome, did you also use an alternative approach to identify SNPs?)

Thank you very much for your participation, your answers and data have been recorded.

Submit your survey.
Thank you for completing this survey.